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JUSTIFICATION OF INSTRUMENTAL BASIS FOR PROVIDING THE MANUFACTURER'S ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETITIVENESS

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Харічков С.К., Аверіхіна Т.В. Обґрунтування інструментальної бази забезпечення екологічної конкурентоспроможності товаровиробників.

В статті викладено авторське бачення питань поглиблення наукових засад та обґрунтування інструментальної бази системи забезпечення екологічної конкурентоспроможності товаровиробників. Метою статті є обґрунтування новітніх підходів щодо забезпечення екологічної конкурентоспроможності товаровиробників на основі запровадження інструментальної бази системи забезпечення екологічної конкурентоспроможності.

Ключові слова: конкурентоспроможність товару та товаровиробника, екологічна конкурентоспроможність, забезпечення екологічної конкурентоспроможності, організаційне забезпечення, інструментальне забезпечення, система інструментів забезпечення

Kharichkov S.K., Averykhina T.V. Justification of instrumental basis for providing the manufacturer's environmental competitiveness.

In the article the author's vision for deepening the scientific basis and justification tool base system of ecological competitiveness of producers. The article aims to study new approaches to ensure the environmental competitiveness of producers from introducing instrumental base system of environmental competitiveness.

Keywords: competitive products and producers, environmental competitiveness, ensuring environmental competitiveness, organizational support, instrumental support, system maintenance tools

The transition of the domestic economy to the strategic goals of development on the basis of sustainability involves improving the tools for responding to changes in the factors of the internal and external environment and the required level of competitiveness (COP) of the national economy in the long run. That is why solving problems of improving the tools for ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises – commodity producers in order to adopt and implement effective management decisions aimed at maximizing the results of their activities in a competitive market, is of particular importance.

First of all, it is about reaching the goals of intensifying the entry of new business entities into commodity markets, increasing the level of satisfaction of consumers' needs in goods and services, raising the level of competitiveness of the national economy, making decisions on economic policy, taking into account the goals and objectives of developing an effective competitive environment and effective competition, as well as the formation of a positive attitude to market competition as a fundamental social value.

Achieving the desired level of the commodity producer's competitiveness is possible only subject to the implementation of appropriate effective mechanisms for its provision.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The research of this problem is devoted to the scientific works of domestic scientists of Kyiv, Sumy, Odessa, Donetsk, Lutsk and other scientific centers of research on the problems of the economy of nature management: Ilyashenko S.M. [1] Melnyk L.G. [2], Petrovskaya S.A. [3], Prigarius I.O. [4], Lukyanenko D.G., Poruchyk A.M. [5], Alexandrova I.O. [6], Kharkikova S.K. [7].

However, studies on the construction of system content and the structural architecture of the instrumental provision of environmental competitiveness of commodity producers are still at an early stage and require further deepening and development.

The purpose of the article is to substantiate the latest approaches to ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers through the introduction of an instrumental base of the system for ensuring environmental competitiveness.

The main part

One of the most important elements of a comprehensive system for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers is the expert environment that determines the instrumental provision (in the broadest sense of the word, from the formation of prerequisites for the acquisition by the producers of objective evidence of environmental competitiveness to further its growth at all stages of the product's lifecycle).

Such a definition of the place and the functional purpose of the instrumental provision is due to his mission as "the philosophy of work in a market" [8], which focuses on:

- understanding consumer needs and trends in their development;
- knowledge of behavior and market development trends;
- knowledge of the environment and trends of its transformation;
- the ability to create such a new product, so that the buyer would prefer it to all other products of competitors;
- the skill to do all this on a long-term, perspective-based basis.

The reasoned basis for a full and effective presentation of author's recommendations on the construction of system content and structural architecture of the instrumental provision of commodity producers' ecological competitiveness can be used as the most adequate from the point of view of functional features, a systematic review of well-known environmental policy tools that regulate relations in the field of nature management, which is given by the author's team under the direction of D.Sc. Professor I.O. Aleksandrov's work [8].

In the context of our study, the author's proposed classification [8] deserves special attention according to the following features:

- use on the territory of Ukraine: distributed – instruments that have been tested and used in the territory of Ukraine in accordance with the current environmental and resource law and environmental legislation;
- Unpopular – tools that are popular and widely used in environmental protection practices of other countries of the world, as well as tools whose practical application is single, sporadic or untested, but have received theoretical scientific substantiation of expediency of their use and efficiency in solving environmental problems;
- the nature of the impact on the behavior of the nature management's subjects: market – instruments that operate with the expenses and revenues of economic entities, prompting them to change the priorities and methods of activity in order to minimize the technogenic load on the components of the environment; Administrative ones – which are official legal documents approved by state control institutions containing information on direct, policy-making regulation and regulation of relations in the field of nature management on the basis of laws, standards and norms, lists of environmentally hazardous types of economic activity and procedures for preventing negative effects on the environment;
- the main functions: regulatory – tools that encourage business entities to comply with environmental legislation, increase the rationality and efficiency of the use of natural resources, avoid, reduce or refuse activities that impair the quality of the components of the environment; Incentives – tools that encourage business entities to volunteer measures and participate in programs to improve the environmental situation and reduce the environmental impact of the environment; Information – tools that are intended to inform the population about the current state of the environment, trends in the use of natural resources, the level of man-made load from specific methods of production of goods and services and the safety of manufactured products for human health and the quality of natural resources;
- the peculiarities of the tools' use: voluntary instruments – used by economic entities on their own initiative, without coercion, based on the principle of free expression of will; Obligatory instruments – unconditional for implementation and distributed to all economic entities without exception, as a rule, their use is formalized at the legislative level; Common tools equally cover all types of business activities and extend to all physical and legal users of the environment; Specialized – focused on the specifics of a particular industry, type of economic activity, natural resource, etc.;
- the scale of regulation: at the international level, the tools aimed at solving common ecological problems that have become global in scope, and therefore their efforts require joint efforts of many countries of the world, for example, the problem of climate change, transboundary pollution of the atmosphere and water resources; National level – the instruments that are regulated by the legislative and executive authorities are, as a rule, binding and are related to increased rational use, protection and reproduction of natural resources of national importance; Regional level – the instruments, the introduction or change of which may initiate local self-government;
- ability to respond promptly to changes in the conditions of nature use: flexible – the tools that most fully and promptly take into account changes in levels of man-caused stress due to nature use; Inflexible – instruments that have a fixed effect on business entities and react to a delay in their change in their environmental status.

According to the conclusions of the doctor of economic sciences, prof. Alexandrova I.O. In addition, his colleagues [9] according to the nature-resource and ecological legislation of Ukraine and the proposed typology of classification marks, it can be noted that:

- there is a tendency to prevail over market (83.0%), regulating (58.0%) and stimulating (33.0%) environmental management tools and environmental protection;
- priority is given to general-use tools (62.5%) compared to specialized tools (37.5%);
- among the total set of given instruments (48 units) in the sphere of nature management and environment of Ukraine about half (47.9%) are used; Of these, instruments prevail:
 - A) regulatory direction – 78.0%;
 - B) obligatory for performance of all types of business entities – 65.0%;
- according to the level of application and regulatory possibilities, the instruments under study can be used:

- A) at all levels – 12.5%;
 - B) at the international and state levels – 16.7%;
 - C) only at the state level – 39.6%;
 - D) at the state and regional levels – 20.8%;
 - E) only at the regional level – 14.6%;
- the socio-economic tools for regulation of nature-conservation activities in Ukraine are characterized by the prevalence of national instruments (52.2%); Tools for regional designation are absent;
- in accordance with the promptness of responding to changes in the conditions of nature use in Ukrainian practice, the priority (70.0%) is given to the inflexible types of socio-economic levers of management.

The analysis' results of the above-mentioned characteristics of the environmental management instruments' whole range in Ukraine suggest that there is a general tendency towards their orientation to market restrictive instruments, the concentration of control levers at the national level, the predominance of instruments that respond to changes in the technogenic load on the environment with delay.

Consequently, the current situation with the formation of environmental management tools' system can not be considered by any means to be adequate for the automatic use of the proposed instruments in order to ensure the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers and requires the modernization of the instrumental apparatus in order to increase the share of instruments aimed to stimulate the formation and provision of ecological competitiveness of commodity producers capable of operations to react indecisively to the change in the positioning of commodity producers in the markets on the basis of their environmental performance.

In the most general definition, the tools for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers should be understood as certain levers (they implement specific methods) to achieve the required level of environmental competitiveness, completeness, validity and interaction of which should ensure the quality and effectiveness of managerial decisions that predetermine tasks (desired, necessary for positioning On the market) level of competitiveness.

In this case, the instrumental provision of ecological competitiveness as a systemic phenomenon must be constructed if the following objectives are achieved: integration of the system's target orientations, namely, targeting the user's product; coverage and coordination of all stages of the ecological life cycle of products, all stages of its production and all stages of market competition of these objects in the relevant markets; the combination of security, enhancement, sustainability and environmental competitiveness management; anticipating and strategically identifying necessary solutions to prevent possible problems.

The construction of an instrumental system for the environmental competitiveness of commodity producers should be based on the differentiation of the level of environmental competitiveness, which has the following boundary features: "0" – absolute lack of environmental competitiveness; "1" – the maximum, became ecological competitiveness.

Intermediate levels (and appropriate phases) for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers reflect the fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The matrix of relations "types of tools for providing EC – levels of EC"

Source: Own elaboration

In the general cycle of ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers, it is expedient to consistently allocate the zone of origin and formation of ecological competitiveness, the zone of its active growth and the zone of sustainable maintenance of the level necessary and sufficient to achieve leadership in the competitive struggle. The boundary levels of the respective zones are determined by the actual environmental conditions of the commodity producers and the relevant requirements of the markets for the significance of the signs of their environmental friendliness as competitive advantages (in fig. 1, the boundary levels of the designated zones of environmental competitiveness are indicated conventionally for illustrative purposes).

For a constructive construction of a system of tools for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers, a conceptual foundation should serve as a certain analysis of the principles of the formation of such a system and an adequate systematic tool for each of the groups identified above.

First, it is necessary to determine the approaches to identifying the appropriate groups of instruments for ensuring environmental competitiveness. National peculiarities and traditions of implementation of environmental policy in Ukraine confirm the high probability of the identification of the proposed classification of the instruments of ensuring ecological competitiveness with the well-known classification of environmental policy levers for administrative, economic and voluntary [9] recommendations and recommendations for the selection of tools for hard and soft regulation of nature management [10].

Based on this assumption, one can propose the following classification model of tools for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers (fig. 2).

The use of activator tools (they are strictly influenced by intensity) is aimed at direct impact on the environmental parameters of the commodity producers' activity and the products manufactured by them, by observing laws and other regulatory means (standards, regulations, etc.) that will ensure entry and start the positioning of the commodity producer as environmentally competitive in the market.

Assignment of stimulant tools (the intensity of their impact is tangible) is an indirect task of ensuring the achievement of important market positioning targets for companies and strict control over their observance, and the use of incentive-related markets associated with the functioning of sustainable growth of environmental competitive advantages and competitive behavior of actors management in an environmentally relevant direction; such a targeted functional tool – the stimulant determines the freedom of choice of enterprises competing on the grounds of environmental friendliness, effective ways to achieve socially significant ecologically oriented goals.

Fig. 2. Classification of the system of tools for ensuring environmental competitiveness

Source: Own elaboration

Instruments – locks (they are on the basis of the intensity of influence are of a soft character) in the system of ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers are to some extent supplemented by standard administrative, organizational (market-oriented) instruments; they aim at ensuring that the traditional management approaches to environmental competitiveness are limited and that the conditions for maintaining its high level are based on the integrated goal-oriented ensuring of the competitiveness of the commodity producer in the three-dimensional dimension: environmental, economic and social in accordance with the general civilization paradigm of sustainable development.

Regarding the basic principles of ensuring the effectiveness of the system of producers' environmental competitiveness instrumental provision, their next author's modified version (tab. 1) is proposed, which is constructed taking into account the peculiarities of the formation and use of national environmental policy's instruments at the level of enterprises as commodity producers and market actors in the context of national features and the traditions of nature use [10-12].

Table 1. Principles of ensuring the effectiveness of the instrumental environmental competitiveness' system

No.	Principles and substantive content of the principle
1	The principle of effectiveness It envisages the selection of the instrumental environmental competitiveness' system (from the generally accepted practice of environmental policy) of such an aggregate that ensures the achievement of the ultimate goals (corresponding to the desired level of environmental competitiveness) with low-cost resource-saving measures)
2	The principle of justice It focuses on the establishment of a system for ensuring environmental competitiveness on the implementation of those instruments that create the prerequisites for a balanced distribution of consequences (positive, as possible and negative) between the state, enterprises-commodity producers and commodity subjects
3	The principle of realization Determines the need to take into account the factor of mandatory access to information sources and the availability of the necessary amount of necessary information for making appropriate decisions on ensuring environmental competitiveness and monitoring their implementation
4	The principle of promising Characterizes the ability to use tools for ensuring environmental competitiveness in the conditions of strategic measurement (in time) to determine the directions of solving the problem of environmental competition, and in the operational-tactical dimension (in real time and space) to ensure rational behavior of commodity producers in their competition on the basis of Environmental friendliness of goods and industries
5	The principle of flexibility Provides the possibility of mobile adaptation of tools for ensuring environmental competitiveness to change the conditions of the market environment in order to determine the necessary actions on the behavior of competing enterprises-producers in order to save them on the market or to search for new markets on the grounds of their environmental competitiveness
6	The principle of admissibility Displays compliance as a mandatory condition of support and approval for the use of commodity producers to create an instrumental basis for ensuring environmental competitiveness of such instruments, the application of which is not Violates the economic, social and environmental interests of citizens, society, business and the state
7	Principle of complementarity and transformation Provides an effective combination of environmental regulation tools with other instruments of economic, social and technical regulation through the creation of a interconnected balancing system of instrumental provision of environmental competitiveness focused on achieving strategic benchmarks for sustainable socioeconomic and economic development
8	The principle of integration Determines the possibility and necessity (under appropriate conditions) of the development of the tool base of the system for ensuring environmental competitiveness through the integration of mandatory and voluntary instruments of their status, which considerably enhances the capabilities of commodity producers in finding specific directions and solutions to increase their competitiveness on the basis of environmental friendliness
9	The targeting and ranking principle Fixes signs of the functional purpose of those or other instruments of ensuring environmental competitiveness for their application in various areas of environmentalization of goods and commodity producers (materials, technologies, production processes, management, etc.) and ranking these instruments according to the priorities of their intended use as typical, traditionally alternative and Non-traditional ones

Source: Own elaboration

Summarizing the above-mentioned approaches and the basic conditions, the following architectures of the system of tools for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers are proposed (fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Architectonic system of tools for ensuring the ecological competitiveness of commodity producers

Source: Own elaboration

The enterprises-producers of the environmental competitiveness instrumental provision system's use in the real conditions is determined by the strategic functional and target tasks of each proposed instruments.

Conclusions

To summarize, it can be concluded that the effectiveness and efficiency of implementing the system of instrumental provision of the commodity producers' ecological competitiveness is determined by the complex of those functional and target tasks that can be solved by using one or another specific instrument in order to approach the ultimate goal – to ensure conditions for raising and maintaining a certain competitive level of environmental competitiveness of the company-manufacturer among the set of competing on the grounds of eco-labels of market players' objectives.

Abstract

In the article the author's vision for deepening the scientific basis and justification tool base system of ecological competitiveness of producers.

The article aims to study new approaches to ensure the environmental competitiveness of producers from introducing instrumental base system of environmental competitiveness.

One of the most important elements of a comprehensive system of environmental competitiveness of commodity expert community determines the tool support (in the broadest sense of the word – from the formation of the prerequisites entry producers of environmental competitiveness objective evidence to further its growth in all stages of the life cycle of producers). That the efficiency and effectiveness of the instrumental support environmental competitiveness' introduction of the commodity is determined by a set of functional and targets that can be solved through the use of a particular tool for moving closer to the ultimate goal – ensuring conditions improve and that a certain competitive level of environmental competitiveness of enterprises-producers among a plurality of competing on the grounds of environmental business market.

JEL Classification: Q01, Q57.

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